

Exergy Efficiency Analysis of Steam Generator based on Exergy Transfer Method

Ma Xiaoyu, Tian Zhaofei *, Zhang Zhijiang, Jin Yuguan, Qiu Rui
Harbi Engineering University
Harbin Engineering University, 145 Nantong St., Harbin, Heilongjiang, China. 150001
* Email: tian_zf@hrbeu.edu.cn

Abstract: It's necessary to correctly calculate the utilization efficiency of nuclear energy. The attribute of "quality" reflecting the energy consumption in the heat transfer process of steam generator is needed to be studied. In this paper, the exergy efficiency of steam generator's U tube between primary and secondary side is focused on. The exergy transfer method of thermal systems is used based on the second law of thermodynamics. Compared with the traditional exergy analysis method, exergy transfer reflects the phenomenological relationship of the resistance and rate in transfer process. To better explore the irreversible loss mechanism of the real system, this paper innovatively establishes the mathematical model of the exergy transfer process in a natural-recirculating steam generator system. The steam generator is separated into 3 exergy transfer units, and each unit's exergy transfer coefficient is derived. The mathematical model is verified with a typical steam generator in AP1000. Based on relap5/MOD3 which can simulate one-dimensional two-phase thermal parameters, the selected system model is developed. With the output data source (pressure, temperature, flow rate et.) in steady process, exergy transfer method is used to calculate each exergy transfer unit's exergy transfer coefficient, exergy destruction and exergy efficiency with C++ programming. The results showed the steam generator's exergy efficiency is 93.92%.

Key Words: Exergy Transfer, Exergy Analysis, Thermodynamic Simulation, Relap5, Steam Generator

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, since the nuclear electricity supply is increasing, there has been a remarkable resurgence of interest in developing nuclear power plant economy. Correctly analyzing the energy utilization efficiency of nuclear power plant facilities can fully harness the energy-saving potential and promote sustainable development. Overall, the current research on energy-saving and consumption reduction has given suggestions based on taking energy efficiency as the evaluation index. However, it is imperative to make energy usage improvements based on "quantity" and "quality" perspectives. The concept of exergy is based on the first and second law of thermodynamics which can calculate the maximum theoretical capacity of energy to do work and reflect the quality of energy. Compared with the traditional exergy analysis method, exergy transfer takes the interaction between each unit in the system into consideration [1]. It explores the irreversible loss mechanism and considers energy's dynamic characteristics [2].

In this paper, relap5/MOD3 is used to simulate the one-dimensional two-phase natural recirculating steam generator system and get the data source. The heat transfer coefficient of the work medium in steam generator is innovatively derived with the exergy transfer method from "quality" and "quantity" aspects. This paper established the model of each unit's exergy transfer process in SG system. The exergy loss and exergy transfer coefficient at different areas of SG under working conditions are simulated and

calculated. The result is pivotal to providing theoretical and technical guidance for nuclear energy utilization.

Nomenclature

c_p	Specific heat capacity at constant pressure, J/kg K
E_x	Exergy flow rate, MW
G	Mass flow rate, kg/s
K_e	Exergy transfer coefficient, W/m ² K
L	Pipe length, m
P	Pressure, MPa
T	Temperature, K
T_0	Ambient temperature, K
Subscripts	
s1	Primary side
s2	Secondary side
w1	Pipe inner wall
w2	Pipe outer wall
in	inside
out	outside

II. STEAM GENERATOR MODELING AND SIMULATION DETAILS

II.A. Steam Generator Heat Transfer System

In this paper, a typical AP1000 vertical re-circulating steam generator system is selected for the simulation (as shown in Fig. 1). The steam generator is a shell-tube heat exchange equipment that transfers heat from the primary to

the secondary side. This study mainly focuses on the heat transfer situation in the U-tube bundle area of the steam generator. It does not consider the descending section and the upper moisture separator. Based on the heat transfer principles, the process of coolant, inner pipe wall, outer pipe wall, and feedwater are thermally conductive. On the primary side inside of the U-pipe, the high-temperature coolant's heat from the reactor transfers to the U-pipe inner wall with a convection heat transfer process. The inner wall heat transfers to the outer wall with a heat conduction process. In the secondary side ascending channel, it is mainly a two-phase boiling heat exchange process between the feedwater and the U-pipe outer wall. Therefore, as shown in Fig. 2, the shell and pipe area on primary and secondary sides is divided into nodes. By establishing mass, momentum, and energy formulas on each node can solve the temperature and pressure changes.

Fig. 1 Vertical re-circulating type steam generator [3]

Fig. 2 Diagram of Steam Generator U-pipe model

II.B. Dynamic Model of Steam Generator System

In the heat transfer process of steam generator's U pipe, the temperature and pressure field will change with the pipe length. The structural parameters and designed thermal data can be reached with the help of software Relap5/MOD3 which is applied to model thermal hydraulic systems. The main structure and operation parameters are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Main parameters of the AP1000 steam generator [3]

parameters	value	unit
Heat transfer pipe number	10025	-
Thickness of pipe wall	1	mm
u-pipe Inner diameter	15.48	mm
u-pipe outer diameter	17.48	mm
The pipe height	10	m
The pipe length	23.77	m
Primary inlet temperature	321	°C
Secondary inlet temperature	247	°C
Coolant flow rate	7593.154	Kg s-1
Feedwater flow rate	4337.824	Kg s-1

The main governing equations in the relap5/MOD3 model.[4]

(1) Mass continuity equation

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\alpha_f \rho_f) + \frac{1}{A} \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\alpha_f \rho_f v_f A) = \Gamma_f \quad (1)$$

where α_f is the void fraction, rad/s^2 ; A is the cross-sectional area, m^2 ; ρ_f is fluid density, kg m^{-3} ; t denotes the time, s ; v_f is the kinematic viscosity, m^2/s ; Γ_f is the volumetric mass exchange rate, $\text{kg/m}^3 \text{ s}$; x is the spatial coordinate, m .

(2) Momentum conservation equation

$$\alpha_f \rho_f A \frac{\partial v_f}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_f \rho_f A \frac{\partial v_f^2}{\partial x} = -\alpha_f A \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} + \alpha_f \rho_f B_x A - (\alpha_f \rho_f A) FWF(v_f) - (\alpha_f \rho_f A) FIG(v_f - v_g) - C \alpha_f \alpha_g \rho_m A \left[\frac{\partial(v_f - v_g)}{\partial t} + v_g \frac{\partial v_f}{\partial x} - v_f \frac{\partial v_g}{\partial x} \right] \quad (2)$$

where B_x is the body force in x coordinate direction, m/s^2 ; C is the coefficient of virtual mass, $1/\text{K s}$; FWF is the wall drag coefficients, s^{-1} ; FIG is the interphase drag coefficients, s^{-1} ; P denotes the pressure, Pa ; ρ_m is the two-phase mixture work medium's density, kg m^{-3} .

(3) Energy conservation equation

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\alpha_f \rho_f U_f) + \frac{1}{A} \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\alpha_f \rho_f U_f v_f A) = -P \frac{\partial \alpha_f}{\partial t} - \frac{P}{A} \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\alpha_f \rho_f A) + Q_{wf} + Q_{if} + DISS_f \quad (3)$$

Where U_f is specific internal energy, J/kg; $DISS$ is the energy dissipation function, W/m³; Q_{wf} is the volumetric heat addition rate from wall to liquid, W/m³; Q_{if} is the volumetric heat addition rate from wall to vapor, W/m³.

Based on relap5, the model of AP1000's steam generator system is built. Then, the needed data source for exergy efficiency analysis can be generated.

III. EXERGY TRANSFER METHOD IN STEAM GENERATOR SYSTEM BASED ON THE SECOND LAW OF THERMODYNAMICS

III.A. Exergy Equilibrium Model Establishment

Exergy transfer is a thermodynamic analysis method that studies the time-space variation of exergy in the irreversible process of a system, making it easier to find the potential energy improvement points in the system. For the exergy analysis of engineering problems, the first step is to establish the exergy transfer units which include exergy source, exergy flow, and exergy hole. Among them, the exergy source continuously releases exergy flow, and the exergy hole continuously receives exergy flow (the environment can also be considered as the exergy hole). The exergy flow is similar to the properties of energy flow which is the amount of exergy transferred during the exergy transfer process. When two or more exergy units connect with each other, the exergy transfer system is established. As shown in Fig. 3, in the exergy transfer unit1, the high-temperature coolant on primary side is the exergy source, and the U-pipe inner wall is the exergy hole. In exergy transfer unit2, the U-pipe inner wall plays the exergy source role which means this node has dual roles in these two units. In exergy transfer unit3, the U-pipe outer wall is the exergy source to release exergy flow and the feedwater in secondary circuit is the exergy hole to receive exergy flow.

Fig. 3 Exergy transfer unit schematic diagram of the heat transfer process in SG

Fig. 4 Balance model of the steam generator exergy transfer processes

During the heat transfer process between steam generator's primary and secondary sides, the heat is transferred from high temperature work fluid to low temperature one which is an irreversible process. Therefore, it exits irreversible exergy loss. The exergy equilibrium model is established as shown in Fig. 4.

The exergy balance equation of the primary coolant, U-pipe wall and feedwater can be expressed as Eq. (4)-Eq. (6):

$$E_{x,s1in} - E_{x,s1out} = E_{x,s1in} - E_{x,win} + E_{x,loss1} \quad (4)$$

$$E_{x,win} = E_{x,wout} + E_{x,loss2} \quad (5)$$

$$E_{x,bout} = E_{x,s2out} - E_{x,s2in} + E_{x,loss3} \quad (6)$$

The exergy destruction coefficient ξ_i is used to reflect the efficiency of different components in the system. It's the objected components' exergy loss divided by the total thermal output from the primary circuit.[5]

$$\xi_i = \frac{E_{x,loss}}{E_{x,s1in} - E_{x,s1out}} \quad (7)$$

III.B. Exergy Transfer Model Establishment

The exergy transfer phenomenon is caused by the potential difference, such as temperature difference, pressure difference, and so on. The transfer quantity is directly related to the gradient of corresponding factors and meets the phenomenological linear relationship. The basic exergy transfer formula can be summarized as Eq. (8) [2].

$$E_x = -K_e F V P_e \quad (8)$$

Where E_x is the transferred exergy flow rate, MW; K_e is the exergy transfer coefficient (its unit based on the type of potential difference. For example, if the potential is temperature, the unit will be W/m² K); F is the exergy exchange area, m²; P_e is the potential difference.

Assuming:

- (1) the pressure change on primary side is negligible
- (2) Axial exergy transfer at the U-pipe wall is not considered
- (3) Considering heat exchange in the secondary side between feedwater and pipe outer wall as the saturated boiling heat exchange.

The exergy transfer coefficient of the 3 units is derived and described from Eq. (9)-(12). It indicates the amount of exergy that passed through the analyzed area. It is only determined by the natural and exergy transfer unit's structure. The exergy transfer coefficient plays an essential role in the quantity of exergy flow rate which can be used to measure the exergy transfer capacity of the analyzed unit.

The exergy transfer coefficient of the coolant to pipe inner wall:

$$K_{e,w1} = \frac{G_{s1} L C_p (1 - \frac{T_0}{T_{s1,i}}) dT}{F(T_{s1,i} - T_{w1,i}) dx} + \frac{G_{s1} L v_f}{F(T_{s1,i} - T_{w1,i}) dx} \quad (9)$$

$$F = \pi d N \Delta x \quad (10)$$

Where G_{s1} is the primary side coolant's mass flow rate, kg/s; L is the average U-pipe length, m; T_0 is the ambient temperature, K; $T_{s1,i}$ is the primary side temperature in the node, K; F is the heat transfer area, m²; $T_{w1,i}$ is the pipe inner wall temperature in the node, K; P is the pressure, MPa; v_f is the coolant's specific volume, m³/kg.

The exergy transfer coefficient of the pipe inner wall to pipe outer wall:

$$K_{e,w2} = \lambda_w \left[1 - T_0 \frac{\ln(T_{w1,i}/T_0)}{T_{w1,i} - T_0} \right] \quad (11)$$

Where λ_w is the pipe wall's heat transfer coefficient, W/m² K.

The exergy transfer coefficient of the pipe outer wall to secondary side feedwater:

$$K_{e,s2} = \frac{G_{s2} L c_p (1 - \frac{T_0}{T_{s2,i}}) dT}{F(T_{w2,i} - T_{s2,i}) dx} + \frac{G_{s2} v_f [1 + (T_0 - T) \alpha_v] dP}{F(T_{w2,i} - T_{s2,i}) dx} \quad (12)$$

$$\alpha_v = \frac{1}{v} \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial T} \right)_p \quad (13)$$

Where G_{s2} is the secondary side coolant's mass flow rate, kg/s; $T_{s2,i}$ is the secondary side temperature in the node, K; $T_{w2,i}$ is the pipe outer wall temperature in the node, K; α_v is the feedwater's volume expansion coefficient, K⁻¹.

For the coolant, since it is incompressible fluid, its specific volume is constant. The coolant's exergy flow rate is derived as Eq. (14).

$$dE_{x,s1} = G de = G_{s1} \left[c_p \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T_{s1}} \right) dT + v_f dP \right] \quad (14)$$

Based on the abovementioned exergy transfer coefficient, it is easy to see that the exergy flow rate is affected by both exergy transfer coefficient and potential field difference. Therefore, the exergy flow rate of pipe inner wall, pipe outer wall, and secondary side feedwater are as follows, Eq. (15)-(17).

$$E_{x,w1} = - \int_{T_{w1,in}}^{T_{w1,out}} \int_{P_{w1,in}}^{P_{w1,out}} K_{e,w1} F \quad (15)$$

$$E_{x,w2} = -K_{e,w2} F (T_{w2} - T_{w1}) \quad (16)$$

$$E_{x,s2} = - \int_{T_{s2,in}}^{T_{s2,out}} \int_{P_{s2,in}}^{P_{s2,out}} K_{e,s2} F \quad (17)$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

IV.A. Relap5 output data source

Taking the steady-state of a typical AP-1000 steam generator as an example, the heat transfer characteristics are simulated. The temperature variations of the workflows and walls are illustrated in Fig. 5. The initial U-pipe primary side inlet temperature is 313.169°C, and the outlet temperature is

281.069°C. The temperature of the coolant, inner pipe wall, and out pipe wall decreases linearly along the coolant flow rate direction. The secondary side's temperature increased gradually at the initial stage. Then the workflow tends to stabilize in the saturated boiling region. From Fig. 6, it can be seen the secondary side's vapor fraction increased gradually from the water level of 0 to 4m, after reaching the saturated boiling region, the vapor fraction stands still at around 0.496, and the temperature keeps around 273.6 °C.

Fig. 5 Temperature change curves

Fig. 6 Secondary side vapor fraction change

Fig. 7 Pressure change of Primary side

Fig. 8 Pressure change of secondary side

Fig. 11 Exergy flow rate of feedwater

Fig. 9 U-pipe wall's heat transfer coefficient

Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show the pressure variation along the vapor-generated direction. The pressure on the primary side decreased from 15.774MPa to 15.587MPa, the pressure difference is 0.187MPa. The pressure in the secondary side's fluid ascending area decreased from 5.838MPa to 5.794MPa, the pressure difference is 0.044MPa. The pressure difference in the secondary side's ascending area is small as the result of a high vapor fraction. The change of the U-pipe's wall's heat transfer coefficient is depicted in Fig. 9.

IV.B. Exergy Simulation Results

Fig. 10 Exergy flow rate of coolant and pipe inner and outer wall

From Fig. 10, it can be seen the exergy flow rate of coolant, pipe inner wall, and pipe outer wall decreased along the primary workflow's direction. Coolant's exergy flow rate declined from 9715.571 to 8439.516 MW. The pipe inner wall's exergy flow rate decreased from 9659.326 to 8403.07 MW, and the pipe outer wall's exergy flow rate descended from 9579.082 to 8383.641 MW. The variation trends of these three parts are the same which declined gradually and tends to keep still. The exergy flow rate of feedwater increased from 6728.158 to 7926.599 MW. From Fig. 11, it increased rapidly and tends to keep still after 4m (the saturated boiling region). Based on Fig. 10, the thermal output of primary side is the exergy variation of the coolant which is 1276.055 MW. According to Eq. (4) to (6), the exergy loss of each unit is shown in table2.

Table 2

Exergy loss and coefficient of each unit

	Exergy loss (MW)	Exergy loss coefficient
Exergy transfer Unit1	19.799	0.0155
Exergy transfer Unit2	23.502	0.0184
Exergy transfer Unit3	34.313	0.0269
Total	77.614	0.0608

Therefore, the total steam generator's exergy efficiency is 93.92%. Compared with its energy efficiency which is 95.24%, it provides a correct and accurate result and gives a reference for the energy conservation potential.

Fig. 12 Exergy transfer coefficient of exergy transfer unit 1

Fig. 13 Exergy transfer coefficient of exergy transfer unit2

Fig. 14 Exergy transfer coefficient of exergy transfer unit3

Fig. 12 to Fig. 15 shows the exergy transfer coefficient change curve of the three analyzed units of steam generator system. The exergy transfer coefficient increases with the height of the pipe. For exergy transfer unit1, it increased from 28.201 to 748.325 W/m² K. When it comes to exergy transfer unit2, it increased from 17.722 to 404.039 W/m² K. And the exergy transfer coefficient of unit3 increased from 18.354 to 72.606 W/m² K. From unit 1 to unit 3, the exergy coefficient declined.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the steam generator's U-pipe is taken as the research object. The mathematical model of the SG heat transfer process is established. Based on Relap5/MOD3 software, the temperature and pressure field change process in the heating process of workflow on primary and secondary sides are simulated and analyzed. Based on the exergy transfer theory, the exergy change in the steady state is analyzed and the exergy transfer coefficient in three exergy transfer units is obtained. The following conclusions can be made.

(1) Compared Fig. 5 with Fig. 10, it's apparent that the changing trends of exergy flow rate are the same as the

variation trends of the temperature. Therefore, the exergy flow rate is highly affected by temperature during the heat transfer process.

(2) Different from heat transfer coefficient, the exergy transfer coefficient is more affected by the potential difference. The leading potential field is temperature. From Fig. 5, and Fig. 12 to Fig. 14, it can be seen the exergy transfer coefficient increased sharply with the decrease of temperature difference. Based on the definition of exergy transfer coefficient which indicates the object's exergy transfer capacity, the higher the exergy transfer coefficient, the less exergy loss. Therefore, to reduce the heat transfer temperature difference is an efficient way to improve the energy use efficiency.

(3) The exergy coefficient curve's changing trends are consistent with the reality which proves the feasibility of exergy transfer theory.

(4) The total exergy loss of steam generator system is 93.92%. Compared with the traditional thermal analysis method which the thermal efficiency is 95.24%, it gives a new understanding of the actual available energy loss and location. This analysis method is conducive to optimize the design and configuration of Nuclear Power Plant energy system to improve the overall efficiency in the future.

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